

Studies in some Amino-Acid Chelates: Part-I

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The stepwise formation constants of the chelates of glycine, α -alanine and β -alanine with Ni(II), VO(II) and Zn(II) have been determined by Irving-Rossotti method and the values have been interpreted in terms of the nature of the metal ions and the ligands.

Amino acids have been known to form specific ring compounds with a number of metal ions which fall under the class of inner complex salts. Glycine and alanine are universally accepted as chelating agents¹⁻⁴. In β -alanine, however, there is an abrupt fall in the tendency to form complex and very few compounds have been reported. Nakamoto *et al.*⁵ have studied the infra-red spectra of the amino acid chelates. Recently McAulifee and Perry⁶ have reported the hydrated and anhydrous chelates of amino acids. Literature survey indicates that Irving-Rossotti method has not been used to study these chelates. The present study of the formation constants of Ni(II), VO(II) and Zn(II) chelates with glycine, α and β -alanine has, therefore, been undertaken.

Glycine (Rienal, Germany), α and β -alanines (B.D.H.) used were A.R. pure. In order to avoid the complexing tendencies of the anions, metal perchlorates Ni(ClO₄)₂ and Zn(ClO₄)₂ have been prepared and its metal content have been determined. However, VOCl₂ (B.D.H.) pure was used, as the attempt to prepare the perchlorate oxidises the tetravalent vanadium. Other reagents used were sodium perchlorate (Fluka), perchloric acid (B and A) and sodium hydroxide (S. Merck). All the solutions have been prepared in conductivity water.

Metrohm pH meter type E 350 A (accuracy ± 0.05) was employed for all pH measurements. The titrations were carried out at 25° using a constant temperature bath ($\pm 0.1^\circ$).

The stepwise formation constants were determined by Irving-Rossotti method⁷. From the set of three curves \bar{n}_H , \bar{n} and pL were calculated by using the equations given in the original paper⁷. Values of the proton ligand stability constants are required for the calculation of pL . They have been determined under experimental conditions. For the calculation of K_1^H and K_2^H ; pH was plotted against $\log \bar{n}_H/(1-\bar{n}_H)$ in the two different regions where $\bar{n}_H < 1$ and $1 < \bar{n}_H < 2$. Two straight lines are thus obtained. At the points falling on the straight lines $K^H = pH + \log(\bar{n}_H/1-\bar{n}_H)$. The average values of K_1^H and K_2^H , thus obtained have been tabulated. They are almost same as the values reported using other methods⁸.

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TABLE 1

Ligand	K_1^H	K_2^H
Glycine	$9.60 \pm (0.02)$	$2.33 \pm (0.03)$
α -Alanine	$9.73 \pm (0.02)$	$2.31 \pm (0.01)$
β -Alanine	$10.20 \pm (0.02)$	$3.51 \pm (0.01)$

The formation curves obtained by plotting \bar{n} against pL do not show significant flattening at $\bar{n} = 1$ indicating that the spreading factor is low. The values of K_1 and K_2 obtained at half integral points will, therefore, be too approximate. The step-wise formation constants have been obtained by least square method⁹.

In the case of β -alanine complexes the values of \bar{n} did not go beyond 1 and the least square calculations yielded negative values of $\beta_2 (K_1 K_2)$, indicating that the second stage of formation does not start in this range. The values of K_1 have therefore been determined by the plot of $\log (1 - \bar{n}/\bar{n})$ vs pL (for $\bar{n} < 1$). At the points falling on the straight line $K_1 = pL - \log (1 - \bar{n}/\bar{n})$. The average values of the formation constants have been tabulated below with standard deviation in brackets.

TABLE 2

Metal ion	Glycine least square		α -Alanine least square		β -Alanine linear plot
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_1$
Nickel	$5.86 \pm (0.06)$	$4.98 \pm (0.10)$	$5.85 \pm (0.05)$	$4.49 \pm (0.1)$	5.28
Vanadyl	$8.24 \pm (0.05)$	$7.42 \pm (0.04)$	$8.34 \pm (0.19)$	$7.29 \pm (0.18)$	8.34
Zinc	$5.24 \pm (0.08)$	$4.41 \pm (0.08)$	$5.16 \pm (0.08)$	$4.10 \pm (0.14)$	5.15

The formation constants of the VO(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) glycinate and α -alanine are in agreement with the Irving-William order¹⁰ and are almost in agreement with the values reported earlier by other methods¹¹. Vanadyl (II) ion is found to be forming more stable complexes. It can be expected because in the tetravalent state the electronegativity will be high. The two charges are neutralised by combination with the oxygen. Oxygen being electronegativity, the electron will shift more towards it and thus create lowering of electron density around the vanadium ion. As expected^{3,12}, in cases of all the three metal ions, the order of the stability of the chelates is glycinate \approx α -alaninate $>$ β -alaninate.

Thanks are due to Prof. S. M. Sethna, Head, Chemistry Department, M. S. University of Baroda, for providing laboratory facilities. Thanks are also due to University Grants Commission for the award of research scholarship to one of the authors (M.V.C.).

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Received February 16, 1970

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